

**RESEARCH AND RESOURCES IN LANGUAGE TEACHING:
MOTIVATING LEARNING by
JILL HADFIELD AND ZOLTÁN DÖRNYEI -
BOOK REVIEW**

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In this article, I would like to summarize the book, entitled '*Motivating Learning*'. The names of the authors of this academic book are **Jill Hadfield** and **Zoltán Dörnyei**. Jill Hadfield is an associate professor in the Department of Language Studies at Unitec in New Zealand. Zoltán Dörnyei is a professor of psycholinguistics at the School of English at University of Nottingham. This book was published by the Pearson Education Limited in the United Kingdom. It was first published in 2013. The International Standard Book Number of the printed version of this book is 978-1-4082-4970-3. The International Standard Book Number of the eText version of this book is 978-0-273-78612-2. The International Standard Book Number of the pdf version of this book is 978-0-273-78617-7. As it is written on the second page of this book, catalogue record for the print edition is available from the British Library.

In the preface part of this book, Candlin and Hadfield (2013: p. X) state that;

"All educators will know that motivation is a vital element in learning. In fact, motivation, or the lack of it, is the most commonly cited explanation for success or failure in language learning. This book presents a new theory of motivation based on a vision of the Ideal Future L2 Self. If students have a rich and inspiring vision of the language learner they could become, it argues, they will be motivated to work hard to actualise the vision and become that learner. The book explores how the various components of the theory could be structured into a teaching sequence. It offers a variety of imaginative classroom activities designed to go from creation of the initial vision of the L2 Self to actualisation of the vision through goal setting, task identification, selection of

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appropriate learning strategies and time management. Activities have both motivation building and language learning aims so that teachers can use them in a variety of ways. The book offers suggestions for selecting activities according to teaching context to design a 'motivational programme', and for integrating such a programme into the language syllabus. Finally it presents ideas for using the activities in the book as a basis for action research."

This book has four parts. The title of the first part of this book is **From Research to Implications**. The sub-titles of the first part of this book are as follows: Motivation and the Vision of Knowing A Second Language, Motivation and the Self, A Visionary Motivational Programme, How This Book is Structured.

In this part, it has been denoted by Hadfield and Dörnyei (2013: p. 4) that;

"Past research has shown that the motivational capacity of one's vision-that is, future self-guides-is not automatic: it becomes an effective motivator only if some conditions are in place:

- *The learner does not have a desired future self-image: not everyone is expected to possess a developed ideal or ought-to-self-guide.*
- *The future self-image is elaborate and vivid: a possible self-insufficient specificity and detail may not be able to evoke the necessary motivation.*
- *The future self-image is perceived as plausible: possible selves need to be perceived as possible; otherwise, they remain at the level of sheer fantasy. Yet, they cannot be perceived as comfortably certain either, or else the learner will not feel pressed to exert effort.*
- *The future self-image does not clash with the expectations of the learner's family, peers and other elements of the social environment. (c.f. the detrimental group norm of 'language learning is girly').*
- *The future self-image regularly activated in the learner's working self-concept through various reminders.*
- *The future self-image is accompanied by relevant and effective procedural strategies that act as a roadmap towards the goal; even if an athlete manages to enthuse him/herself by envisaging success, he/she will need a training plan and a coach to channel the released energies onto a productive path.*
- *A desired future self-image is offset by a counteracting feared possible self in the same domain; that is, failing to reach the possible self has negative consequences.*

Becoming aware of these conditions is of great significance, because we genuinely believe that, if these conditions are met, motivation arises automatically and powerfully."

The title of the second part of this book is **From Implications to Application**. The sub-titles of this part are as follows: **1. Content selection 2. Sequencing 3. Where to Find Out More**. In the second part of this book, there are three chapters. The title of the first chapter is **Imaging Identity: My Future L2 Self**. In this chapter, there are five sections. The titles of these sections are the following: **1. Creating the Vision 2. Substantiating the Vision: What is possible 3. Counterbalancing the Vision 4. Unifying the Vision 5. Enhancing the Vision**

In the first chapter of this book, it has been mentioned by Hadfield and Dörnyei (2013: p.12):

"For most of us, there is an obvious discrepancy between the current/actual self and the ideal future self. Self-discrepancy theory states that people will be motivated to reduce this discrepancy so that their current self begins to approach their vision of their ideal self. Motivation thus consists of the desire to reduce the gap between present and ideal selves. In order for the discrepancy to be perceived and thus for his desire to exist; there will need to be some kind of a vision of what the ideal future self is.

Most people have some idea of an ideal future self, but this may not be substantial, elaborate or vivid enough to motivate them. It is important therefore to work on raising awareness of an individual's future desired self, on building up the image and making it as detailed and vivid an imagined reality as possible."

In the first section of the first chapter of this book, there are eight activities. The titles of these activities are as follows: **Activity 1. Future Alternatives Activity 2. Introduction to Visualisation Activity 3. My Ideal Self Activity 4. Portraits Activity 5. L2 Greetings Activity 6. My Future L2 Self Activity 7. Identity Tree Activity 8. The Self I Can Become**.

In this section, the following sample classroom activity has been shared by Hadfield and Dörnyei (2013: p.16):

Activity 1: Future Alternatives

Aim: To provide examples of different Ideal L2 Selves

Level: Intermediate up

Time: 40 minutes

Materials: Reading Texts and Worksheet

Preparation: *Make Enough Copies of Each Text for a Quarter of the Class.*

Make One Copy of the Worksheet for Each Student

Language Practice

Functions:	<i>Future Wishes</i>
Skills:	<i>Reading, Speaking</i>
Language areas:	<i>Present Simple, Would like, Want to</i>

Procedure

1. *Divide students into four groups and give out different texts to each group. Give each student a worksheet.*
2. *Get them to work individually to complete Question 1 and 2, and then compare their answers with their group.*
3. *Get them to make brief notes to summarise their text.*
4. *Regroup the students to make new groups, each having four students who have all read different texts. The easiest way to do this is to give each students in each group number: 1,2,3,4,5, etc. Then regroup them by saying .”All the ones from each group come and sit here, all the twos over here “, and so on.*
5. *Get the students to roleplay being the writer of their text and to tell the others about their ideal future self.*
6. *Get them to discuss which vision, or parts of visions, are most like their own.*

There are six activities in the second section of this chapter. The titles of the activities are as follows: **Activity 9.** Reality Check 1 **Activity 10.** Reality Check 2 **Activity 11.** Reality Consensus **Activity 12.** Dream On! **Activity 13.** Leaf Rating **Activity 14.** Vision Revision

In this section, Hadfield and Dörnyei (2013: p.32) denotes;

“Substantiating the vision means subjecting the original vision of the ideal future self to a reality check to make sure it is plausible and realistically achievable.”

It has also been stated by Hadfield and Dörnyei (2013: p. 32):

“Even the most elaborate, detailed and intensely desired vision of an ideal future self will be meaningless if it is so unrealistic as to be unachievable. Any effective future self must be a possible self; therefore the point of imagining an ideal future self is not to indulge in

idle fantasy but to construct a future possible reality that can be planned for and worked towards."

In the third section, there are seven activities. The following are the activities in the third section of this chapter: **Activity 15.** What if...? **Activity 16.** What Gets in the Way of Learning? **Activity 17.** Identifying the Self Barrier **Activity 18.** Meeting the Self Barrier **Activity 19.** Filmshots **Activity 20.** Two Roads **Activity 21.** Overcoming Obstacles

As Hadfield and Dörnyei (2013: p. 47) mentions that;

"Counterbalancing the vision means that the vision of the ideal self should be balanced against a consideration of what would happen if the desired self were not attained."

In the same chapter, Hadfield and Dörnyei also (2013: p. 47) state that;

"Psychologists have found that motivation consists of two tendencies: approach and avoid. You can probably recognise this in your everyday life; there are goals you want to attain (e.g. getting fit, getting promotion at work) and undesired outcomes you wish to avoid (e.g. becoming unhealthy, remaining on a lower salary). Envisioning the ideal future self is obviously an 'approach' tendency since motivation consists of the desire to approach the goal. Considering what would happen if the desired self were not attained would employ the avoid strategy since motivation would consist of the desire to avoid a negative outcome."

The definition of unifying the vision is given in the fourth section of this chapter. The titles of the activities in the fourth section are as follows: **Activity 22.** Introducing the Ought-to Self **Activity 23.** The Mom Song **Activity 24.** The Ought-to Self Song **Activity 25.** Great Expectations **Activity 26.** Advice From the Ought-to-Self **Activity 27.** Making Friends with the Ought-to Self **Activity 28.** Meeting the Mentor **Activity 29.** The Fourth Man.

In this section, the following classroom activity has been suggested by Hadfield and Dörnyei (2013: p. 92):

Activity 29: The Fourth Map

Aim: To raise interest in the concept of self-guides

Level: Intermediate up

Time: 30 minutes

Materials: Text

Preparation: Copy one text for each group of 4-5 students; cut it up so that there are three sections: (a) Paragraph 1, (b) Paragraph 2, (c) Paragraphs 3 and 4

Language Practice

Functions:	narrative, description
Skill Skills:	reading, discussion
Lan Language area:	present simple, past simple, past perfect

Procedure

1. Ask students to brainstorm real-life heroes/heroines who have found themselves in difficult or extreme circumstances (e.g. Hillary on the ascent to Everest, Florence Nightingale, Amundsen on expedition to South Pole, Lindbergh on first transatlantic flight, Reinhold Messner on first ascent of Everest without oxygen, Yuri Gagarin or Neil Armstrong on space voyage).
2. Ask them:
 - What was the hero/heroine's ideal self and feared self?
 - What could be the self-barriers?
 - What kept them going?
3. Divide students into groups of 4-5. Give each group the first paragraph of the text. Ask them to discuss what the 'Third Man Factor' could be.
4. Give half of each group the second paragraph of the text and the other half the third and fourth paragraphs. Get them to read and to transfer the information.
5. Ask the groups to discuss-in what ways is the 'Third Man' like an ought-to self?

In the fifth section, there are four activities. These are as follows: Activity 30. Future Photo Album **Activity 31.** Future Self-Portraits Activity **32.** Song of My Future Self **Activity 33.** Fairytale.

The second chapter starts on the 105th page and finishes on the 197th page. The title of the second chapter of the second part of this book is **Mapping the Journey: From Dream to Reality.** In this chapter, there are four chapters and the following are the titles of these sections:

- From Vision to Goals;

- From Goals to Plans;
- From Plans to Strategies;
- From Strategies to Achievement;

In this chapter, Hadfield and Dörnyei (2013: p. 107) state that;

“The process of identifying goals and ambitions essentially involves analysing and listing. Activity types which help students fulfill this aim are brainstorming, checklists, mindmaps and questionnaires. Examples of how to go about this process may be useful, and these have been provided in the form of a reading text with questions. The process also involves evaluation and discussion of the list of identified goals to ensure that they are achievable, comprehensive and realistic, and guided discussion activities are provided to help students achieve this. The process will also involve some alignment with the prescribed coursebook or existing syllabus to ensure that the goals are congruent with the course scope and sequence. Various classification and sorting activities will help students and teacher analyse which general aims can be met through whole class work and which more individual aims should be the focus of independent study. Finally, the goals determined by the class as a whole and individual students separately need to be made public and displayed as a reminder to give direction and purpose to the course.”

The third chapter starts on the 198th page and finishes on the 284th page. The title of the third chapter is **Keeping the Vision Alive**. In the third chapter, there are two sections and their titles are as follows: **Section 1. Developing Identity** **Section 2. Making It Real**.

In the third chapter, the following classroom activity has been suggested by Hadfield and Dörnyei (2013: pp. 224-225-226-227-228-229):

Activity 79: Role Model Poleplay (Hadfield& Dörnyei, 2013: p. 224)

Aim: *To raise student awareness about what makes a good language learner*

Level: *Intermediate up*

Time: *20-30 minutes*

Materials: *Reading texts and questionnaire*

Preparation: *Copy each reading text for half the class; copy the questionnaire from Activity 77 for everyone*

Language P *Language Practice*

Functions:	<i>talking about habits and routines, describing feelings</i>
Skills:	<i>reading, speaking</i>
Language Areas:	<i>present simple</i>

Procedure

1. *Put students in two groups. Give out reading text A to Group A and text B to Group B.*
2. *Ask students to read the text and ask themselves the question: What can I learn from this person's experience? Allow some time for students to read the text then get them to discuss it in their group.*
3. *Regroup students in pairs so they are with a partner from a different group. Give copies of the questionnaire (from Activity 77) to everyone.*
4. *Students interview each other, asking the questions on the questionnaire, responding as if they are the person who wrote the text.*
5. *The pairs discuss what they found helpful and what strategies they could adopt themselves.*

Text A Successful Language Learner: German (Hadfield & Dörnyei, 2013: pp. 225-226)

Which foreign languages do you speak?

French, German, Italian, Spanish and Chinese.

Which do you speak best?

German.

How did you begin learning the language?

I studied German for two years in high school, then spent a year in Germany After school working in a kindergarten in a hospital. At university, I did a diploma in German as my minor.

I feel benefited from two very different ways of learning a language. The schoolwork was very traditional grammar-translation methodology with an emphasis on accuracy-nearly all reading and writing with very little speaking. When I worked in Germany, on the other hand, there was little reading and writing-only listening and speaking. And no one corrected me! Though I knew when I wasn't communicating successfully by the blank looks on people's faces!

So this was a much more intuitive way of learning the language-just by picking it up with the emphasis on fluency not accuracy. I paid no attention to grammar, but picked up 'chunks' of language, whole phrases and expressions, which I enjoyed inserting into what I was saying and which gave me the feeling of being 'authentic'! Sometimes I had not much idea of what these pieces of language actually meant. Beziehungswaise was one example. I could not have translated it, but from having heard it used so much, knew exactly how to use it and using it made me feel really 'German'. I feel I learned much more that way. But I wonder, though, how much I would have learned and how difficult it would have been, particularly in the initial stages, if I had not had that basic grounding in grammar.

What made you want to continue?

Getting a job in Germany between school and university.

What kept you going through difficult patches?

Wanting to communicate with people.

If you had a vision of yourself as a future user of the language, what was this?

I had a vision of myself as a fluent communicator, making friends and having meaningful conversations. I found it very exciting to be living abroad and having a sense of myself as a European. I feel that this was my adventurous self, also a more sophisticated self, a more intellectual self. The deep and meaningful conversations were definitely a part of my L2 self. I wanted to go to university in Germany (though ended up going back to Britain) so I suppose my future L2 self was a university student.

Do you have any effective ways of studying?

I had two different ways of learning. At school, I was systematic about learning vocabulary and grammar; when I lived in Germany I just 'went with the flow'-just tried to speak and listen as much as possible, without being inhibited or afraid to try things out. At university I combined the two ways: I tried to do as much reading (stories, novels, newspapers) as possible-I found that reading a lot outside class really improved my vocabulary-and also to speak some German with German students to keep up my fluency, as well as the more formal classwork, which focused on translation and interpreting, where I went back to learning vocabulary and focusing more on accuracy-trying to learn from mistakes.

A Hungarian proverb says: “You are as many people as the languages you speak. “When you speak a foreign language, do you feel like a different person in some way? How?

My ‘German Self ’? Yes, very different from my English Self! Much more intense, intellectual, more given to theorizing, more prone to abstractions. Less flippant, less ironic. It probably helped that I was about 19 at the time and in a university city with a strong café culture-full of intense late night discussions! Incidentally, my ‘French self’ is also more analytic and theoretical. It is possibly something of a combined ‘Euroself’-no accident that both countries have a great tradition of philosophy.

Do you feel speaking another language adds anything to your life? What?
Definitely! It’s like an extension of your personality, a window onto a different way of looking at the world.

Text B Successful Language Learner: French (Hadfield& Dörnyei, 2013: pp. 227-228-229)

Which foreign languages do you speak?

French, intermediate German, low-intermediate Russian (a long time ago), beginner Spanish, Mandarin, and basic Maori!!! Reading skills: Portuguese, Italian.... sort of.

Which do you speak best?

French.

How did you begin learning the language?

At kindergarten! Brilliant teacher who taught us a little French each day aged 3-4-5. I remember things in the classroom were labelled ‘la fenêtre, ‘la porte, etc.

Then I learned in a more formal way from the age of 8 at primary school. Inspiring teachers, including the ‘senior’ one who was a very good speaker, wore a beret, was kind and supportive. Very traditional grammar-translation text-based teaching, but he made it fun too, encouraging a bit of creativity-for those days perhaps revolutionary.

What made you want to continue?

Doing well at school I suppose, but also the fact that my father was a fluent French speaker (having attended Lausanne University in his twenties) and spoke French with business associates who frequently came to the house. We had a French girl or two staying (au pairs or school exchange) when I was aged 6-7-8. Ski trips to Switzerland-trains down through France with the multilingual signs.

I was exposed to European languages as background noise through my early years-French, German (Schweizerdeutsch) and Italian. I used to mumble to myself in 'foreign language' when I was 9-10 pretending to be an international spy... Also, in 1961-62 we had two family summer holidays in France and I remember being delighted to be understood talking to some fisherman landing their catch at Barfleur. Quite early-14 or 15-I decided that if I went to university, I'd like to follow my father and go to Lausanne... hopes dashed when the international fees were known but I think my father was encouraging-he thought languages would be as useful for 'business' as they had been to him.

What kept you going through difficult patches?

I suppose I was 'good at exams' and good at French, Latin, so it was not, as far as I can recall, ever a struggle... UNTIL I first went to France on my own and discovered that I could not easily order a drink in a café, even though I could read Racine in the original! This was a shock. And in Paris, after two years at university, I went to a film on my first night-couldn't understand a word (discovered at the end it was all in Quebecois!).

If you had a vision of yourself as a future user of the language, what was this?

- *James Bond spy character able to use many languages perfectly (age 10 or so).*
- *Living in France and able to function 100% in French (from 0 Levels onwards, aged 16).*
- *Maybe transferring culture/nationality from British to French (I was very pro-European) (A levels onwards).*
- *Living and working in France.*

Did you have any effective ways of studying?

Can't remember really-too long ago. Lots and lots of reading in schooldays obviously gave me a firm foundation in vocabulary, grammar, registers... Oral skills came later, inevitably, and I don't think I ever fully caught up (i.e. my writing+reading skills are stronger than my spoken and listening given though I have spent six plus years living in Francophone countries (France and Madagascar). I actively ENJOY using a dictionary and doing translations, so am good at 'small-scale' stuff as well as lengthier tasks (TV, cinema, discussions, reading novels). My schooling, and being good at Latin and French, means I do NOT find that sort of work is my 'comfort zone' and interestingly where I feel 'safe' in my present attempts to learn Maori!

A Hungarian proverb says: "You are as many people as the languages you speak." When you speak a foreign language, do you feel like a different person in some way? How?

Yes, most definitely. It is a form of 'roleplay' or acting. My French is good enough for me to have had interesting conversations with many people at different stages of my life, and I even found I think different kinds of thoughts when 'in French'- more alert intellectually, more 'dialectic', more prone to take a hardline attitude to a problem (political, aesthetic, whatever). I find I enjoy arguing more in French than in English.

Do you feel speaking another language adds anything to your life? What?

Most definitely. The impression of crossing a threshold into a different culture, the opportunity to explore that culture as it were 'from the inside'. Like going into a cave and finding it full of light and fantastic new things to play with-maybe this is an image from King Solomon's mines (Rider Haggard). A very attractive proposition, stepping outside one's 'normal' (English) self and into a different role. Why this should be attractive I don't know-sounds very Freudian somehow!

The third part of this book starts on the 285th page and finishes on the 296th page. The title of the third part of this book is **From Application to Implementation**. The sub-titles of this part are: **1. Towards A Motivational Programme 2. Induction Module 3. Mapping the Journey 4. Keeping the Vision Alive 5. Enjoyment of the Learning Experience 6. Where to Go From Here.**

The fourth part of this book is the final part. The title of the fourth part is **From Implementation to Research**. The sub-titles of the fourth part are as follows: **1. Why Do Action Research? 2. What is Action Research? 3. Who Should Do it? 4. How? 5. Interviewing 6. Interview Topics and Questions 7. Processing the Interview Data 8. Further Reading.**

In this part, Hadfield and Dörnyei (2013: p.292) state that;

"Any language learning experience consists of a complex relationship between the teacher, the student group, the subject being taught and the learner's sense of self. Enjoyment of the learning experience thus consists of four interrelated areas;

- *Enjoyment of the teacher's experience and rapport between students and teacher*
- *Enjoyment of the learning group and class climate*
- *Enjoyment of the subject matter and teaching approach*
- *Enjoyment of success and self-esteem.*

"The absence of any one of these will have a demotivating effect."

Motivation is crucial in foreign language learning. This book explains why and how it is important in learning. Finding many resources on foreign language learning is a great opportunity to foreign language educators or trainers. Classroom activities in this book are related with different language levels and different topics. Users of this book are legally given permission to photocopy the worksheets for the suggested classroom activities on this book. As they are for different age and different language level groups, they can be used for any language level.

As a result, it can be said that this book can be very useful for the readers who would like to use these classroom activities in their classes. It is certain that this book has inspired many foreign language teachers or professors to study or work more on their professions. It has also increased the enthusiasm in many classrooms in the world.

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